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Machine learning approach for predicting *Fusarium culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* growth and mycotoxin production in treatments with ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer films containing pure components of essential oils

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Abstract:	<p><i>Fusarium culmorum</i> and <i>F. proliferatum</i> can grow and produce, respectively, zearalenone (ZEA) and fumonisins (FUM) in different points of the food chain. Application of antifungal chemicals to control these fungi and mycotoxins increases the risk of toxic residues in foods and feeds, and induces fungal resistances. In this study, a new and multidisciplinary approach based on the use of bioactive ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer (EVOH) films containing pure components of essential oils (EOCs) and machine learning (ML) methods is evaluated. Bioactive EVOH-EOC films were made incorporating cinnamaldehyde (CINHO), citral (CIT), isoeugenol (IEG) or linalool (LIN). Several ML methods (neural networks, random forests and extreme gradient boosted trees) and multiple linear regression (MLR) were applied and compared for modeling fungal growth and toxin production under different water activity (a_w) (0.96 and 0.99) and temperature (20 and 28 °C) regimes. The effective doses to reduce fungal growth rate (GR) by 50, 90 and 100% (ED 50, ED 90, and ED 100) of EOCs in EVOH films were in the ranges 200 – >3330, 450 – >3330, and 660 – >3330 µg/fungal culture (25 g of partly milled maize kernels in Petri dish), respectively, depending on the EOC, a_w and temperature. The type of EVOH-EOC film and EOC doses significantly affected GR in both species and ZEA and FUM production. Temperature also affected GR and a_w only affected GR and FUM production of <i>F. proliferatum</i>. EVOH-CIT was the most effective film against both species and ZEA and FUM production. Usually, when the EOC levels increased, GR and mycotoxin levels in the medium decreased although some treatments in combination with certain a_w and temperature values induced ZEA production. Random forest models predicted the GR of <i>F. culmorum</i> and <i>F. proliferatum</i> and ZEA and FUM production better than neural networks or extreme gradient boosted trees. The MLR mode provided the worst performance. This is the first approach on the ML potential in the study of the impact that bioactive EVOH films containing EOCs and environmental conditions have on <i>F. culmorum</i> and <i>F. proliferatum</i> growth and on ZEA and FUM production. The results suggest that these innovative packaging systems in combination with ML methods can be promising tools in the prediction and control of the risks associated with these toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins in food.</p>

Highlights

Machine learning methods were tested to predict *Fusarium* spp. growth and mycotoxin production

Random forest models showed better predictive performance than NN, XGBoost or MLR

EVOH films with CIT, CINHO or IEG are promising candidates for antifungal packaging material

Bioactive EVOH films with CIT, CINHO or IEG notably inhibited ZEA and FUM production

Antifungal effect of these films depends on temperature, film type, dose and fungal species

1 **Machine learning approach for predicting *Fusarium culmorum* and *F.***
2 ***proliferatum* growth and mycotoxin production in treatments with ethylene-**
3 **vinyl alcohol copolymer films containing pure components of essential oils**

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21 **Abstract**

22

23 *Fusarium culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* can grow and produce, respectively,
24 zearalenone (ZEA) and fumonisins (FUM) in different points of the food chain.
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26 the risk of toxic residues in foods and feeds, and induces fungal resistances. In this
27 study, a new and multidisciplinary approach based on the use of bioactive ethylene-
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29 (EOCs) and machine learning (ML) methods is evaluated. Bioactive EVOH-EOC
30 films were made incorporating cinnamaldehyde (CINHO), citral (CIT), isoeugenol
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32 extreme gradient boosted trees) and multiple linear regression (MLR) were applied
33 and compared for modeling fungal growth and toxin production under different water
34 activity (a_w) (0.96 and 0.99) and temperature (20 and 28 °C) regimes. The effective
35 doses to reduce fungal growth rate (GR) by 50, 90 and 100% (ED_{50} , ED_{90} , and ED_{100})
36 of EOCs in EVOH films were in the ranges 200 – >3330, 450 – >3330, and 660 –
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38 respectively, depending on the EOC, a_w and temperature. The type of EVOH-EOC
39 film and EOC doses significantly affected GR in both species and ZEA and FUM
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44 combination with certain a_w and temperature values induced ZEA production.

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51 packaging systems in combination with ML methods can be promising tools in the
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55 Keywords: *Fusarium culmorum*; *Fusarium proliferatum*; zearalenone; fumonisins;
56 machine learning methods; bioactive EVOH-films

57 **1. Introduction**

58 *Fusarium culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* are two common phytopathogenic
59 species that affect food in pre- and post-harvest worldwide. *Fusarium culmorum*
60 (W.G. Smith) Saccardo is one of the main zearalenone (ZEA)-producing species,
61 an estrogen-like compound that binds to the estrogen receptor and causes
62 damage to germ cells and testicular structure (Yang et al., 2018). This species is
63 frequently found in cereals and soybean, among others (Laraba et al., 2017;
64 Wegulo et al., 2015). *F. proliferatum* (Matsushima) Nirenberg is one of the main
65 fumonisin (FUM)-producing species. FUM are toxic compounds associated with
66 leukoencephalomalacia in equine, hepatic and renal toxicity in rodents, pulmonary
67 edema in pigs and esophageal cancer and neural tube defects in humans (Feijó
68 Corrêa et al., 2018). The IARC has classified FUM, mainly fumonisin B1 (FB₁), as
69 possible carcinogenic compounds to humans (Group 2B) (Ostry et al., 2017). *F.*
70 *proliferatum* is found in cereals (Cendoya et al., 2018; Gil-Serna et al., 2013;
71 Stepien et al., 2011), soybean (Chang et al., 2015), date-palm trees (Saleh et al.,
72 2017) or tomato (Gao et al., 2016), among others. So, ZEA and FUM, especially
73 FB₁ and fumonisin B2 (FB₂), are mycotoxins widely distributed in food all over the
74 world (Tarazona et al., 2020a; Waśkiewicz et al., 2012).

75 Although for a long time chemical antifungal agents are being used to
76 control fungal growth and mycotoxin production in food (Magan et al., 2002; Mateo
77 et al., 2013, 2017a; Tarazona et al., 2020b), according to the Food and Agriculture
78 Organization, about 1000 million metric tons of food is spoiled globally each year
79 due to mycotoxins produced by storage molds (Bhat et al., 2010). This problem is

80 exacerbated because consumers demand to minimize chemical additives to inhibit
81 microbial growth in foods while maintaining quality, freshness, and safety.
82 Therefore, new techniques are being developed. In this line, bioactive antimicrobial
83 packaging systems are a possible option and an innovative method to provide
84 increased food safety and quality (Nguyen Van Long et al., 2016). This is a
85 technology that can be used simultaneously with others in the so-called hurdles
86 technology (Suppakul et al., 2003).

87 In recent years, plant products such as essential oils (EOs) and their major
88 bioactive compounds (EOCs), included in the Generally Recognized As Safe
89 (GRAS) category, have been extensively studied as alternatives to synthetic
90 chemicals and different EO formulations are currently assayed or used as food
91 preservatives (da Cruz Cabral et al., 2013; Gómez et al., 2018; Prakash et al.,
92 2015). EOs are produced by more than 17,000 aromatic plant species commonly
93 belonging to angiospermic families Lamiaceae, Rutaceae, Myrtaceae,
94 Zingiberaceae and Asteraceae (Prakash et al., 2015). EO formulations can be
95 added to food directly or by slow release from packaging materials. Among the
96 first, fumigation is one of the best methods to prevent microbial contamination
97 during storage with no/less residual effect. Direct addition of EOs to food causes
98 an immediate reduction of microbial populations. However, if the EO residues are
99 rapidly depleted due to its volatility the recovery of injured cells or the growth of
100 cells that were not destroyed by direct addition may not be prevented. Antimicrobial
101 packaging is a technology that inhibits or retards the proliferation of
102 microorganisms in foods, thus extending the shelf life of the product (Muriel-Galet
103 et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2015). Thus, the application of antimicrobial films

104 containing EOs permits migration of the antimicrobial to the coating surface and
105 provides a continuous antimicrobial effect on the food during extended exposure
106 (Ribeiro-Santos et al., 2017).

107 Ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer containing 29% mol ethylene (EVOH-29)
108 is a packaging material commonly used to provide high oxygen barrier properties.
109 EVOH materials have been used as matrices for the development of active
110 packaging systems, where the polymer protects the active agents during storage
111 and triggers their activity on exposure to a humid environment (the food product)
112 (Catalá et al., 2016; Muriel-Galet et al., 2012). These properties combined with
113 appropriated EOC, could make EVOH a highly suitable material for control of
114 toxigenic fungi (aerobic organisms) and their associated mycotoxins (Mateo et al.,
115 2017a; Tarazona et al., 2018) in food and feed.

116 The growth of toxigenic fungi, including *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum*,
117 and mycotoxin production, mainly depends on temperature, water activity
118 (a_w)/relative humidity (RH) and possible treatments with antifungal agents (Magan
119 et al., 2002, 2003). These factors have also been considered in studies on the
120 effectiveness of bioactive films in controlling fungal growth and mycotoxin
121 production (Mateo et al., 2017a; Tarazona et al., 2018).

122 Machine learning (ML) methods involve many disciplines, such as
123 probability theory, statistics, approximation theory, etc. and supervised ML can be
124 used in prediction analysis (Qu et al., 2019). Predictive models based on ML
125 methods can be innovative tools for the management of toxigenic fungi and
126 mycotoxin production and can help to set preventive treatments. Among such ML
127 methods, artificial neural networks (NN) have been used to predict fungal growth

128 (Panagou et al., 2007; Panagou and Kodogiannis, 2009) or mycotoxin production
129 by fungi (Mateo et al., 2009, 2011a). Random forests (RF) are ensembles of
130 decision trees. They are supervised ML models that have also been applied in
131 mycology for prediction (Breiman, 2001; Meher et al., 2019). Extreme gradient
132 boosted trees (XGBoost) have been applied in a previous mycological study
133 (Tarazona et al., 2020a).

134 The aims of this study were: (1) to evaluate the effect of EVOH-29 films
135 incorporating cinnamaldehyde (CINHO), citral (CIT), isoeugenol (IEG) or linalool
136 (LIN) (pure components of plant essential oils) to control the growth of *F. culmorum*
137 and *F. proliferatum* in partially milled maize under different environmental
138 conditions, (2) to investigate the effects of these treatments and environmental
139 conditions on ZEA production by *F. culmorum* and on FB₁ and FB₂ production by *F.*
140 *proliferatum*, (3) to design ML methods able to predict the growth rates (GR) of
141 these fungi and mycotoxin production under all the assayed conditions.

142 **2. Materials and methods**

143 *2.1. Film preparation*

144 Ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer with 29% ethylene molar content (EVOH-
145 29) was supplied by The Nippon Synthetic Chemical Industry Co., Ltd. (Osaka,
146 Japan). Trans-cinnamaldehyde (3-phenyl-2-propenal) (CINHO), linalool (LIN),
147 isoeugenol (IEG) and citral (CIT) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Barcelona,
148 Spain). The films were made as described by Mateo et al. (2017a). Briefly, films of
149 EVOH with an initial content of 1, 2, 5 and 10% of EOC were prepared by casting

150 in an oven at 75 °C for 15 min. The final content of EOC was determined by
151 thermal desorption-gas chromatography as described by Cerisuelo et al. (2012).
152 The response of the gas chromatograph was calibrated by measuring polyethylene
153 and polypropylene samples with known amounts of CINHO, CIT, IEG and LIN. The
154 additive content is expressed as weight percentage of the compound over dry
155 polymer weight. All the obtained EVOH-29 films containing pure components of
156 plant essential oils were colorless, transparent and continuous. The final contents
157 for CINHO, CIT, IEG or LIN found in the films, were $(0.37 \pm 0.06)\%$, $(0.74 \pm$
158 $0.12)\%$, $(1.85 \pm 0.25)\%$ and $(3.7 \pm 0.5)\%$, w/w of dry polymer, for the films
159 prepared at 1, 2, 5 and 10%, respectively, regardless of the EOC type. The
160 grammage of the bioactive EVOH films was (1.79 ± 0.02) mg/cm². The obtained
161 films were labelled as EVOH-CINHO, EVOH-CIT, EVOH-IEG or EVOH-LIN,

162 2.2. Standards and reagents

163 Mycotoxin standards of ZEA, FB₁, and FB₂ were supplied by Sigma (Sigma–
164 Aldrich, Alcobendas, Spain). Formic acid and ammonium formate were purchased
165 from Panreac (Castellar del Valles, Spain). Acetonitrile and methanol were
166 purchased from J.T. Baker (Deventer, the Netherlands). All solvents were LC
167 grade. Pure water was obtained from a Milli-Q apparatus (Millipore, Billerica, MA,
168 USA) and was used when water was required.

169 2.3. Inoculum preparation

170 *F. culmorum* strain Fc019 and *F. proliferatum* strain Fp06 previously isolated
171 from Spanish maize were used. The strains are held in the Mycology and

172 Mycotoxins Group Culture Collection (Valencia University, Spain). The strains were
173 grown on maize extract medium (MEM) (3% w/v of ground maize kernels + 2% w/v
174 agar in pure water). MEM was sterilized in autoclave (115 °C, 30 min) and
175 transferred into Petri dishes. Five μL of a spore suspension (1×10^6 spores/mL) of
176 each fungal species was inoculated on the center of the plates and incubated at 30
177 °C for 7 days. Conidia of these fresh cultures were used to prepare inocula for
178 further experiments. Before each experiment, a suspension of spores containing
179 1×10^6 conidia/mL, (a Thoma cell chamber counting was used), was prepared in
180 sterile pure Milli-Q water containing Tween 80 (0.005%) (Tarazona et al., 2020b).

181 *2.4. Preparation of fungal culture with different bioactive films and a_w levels*

182 The assays with bioactive EVOH-EOC films were carried out in partially
183 milled maize kernels (25 g) (pieces of 1-3 mm) as indicated by Tarazona et al.
184 (2018). Partially milled maize, previously analyzed to ensure they had undetectable
185 levels of ZEA, FB₁ and FB₂, was placed in Erlenmeyer flasks and autoclaved for 20
186 min at 121 °C. Flasks containing milled maize destined to measure water activity
187 (a_w) values only were run at the same time. Then, milled maize was adjusted to
188 0.99 or 0.96 a_w by adding sterile pure water using specific curves. The a_w -values
189 were measured with a Novasina RTD 502 equipment (Novasina GmbH, Pfäffikon,
190 Switzerland) using controls of known a_w values. The culture media were spread
191 into 9-cm sterile Petri dishes. Then, circular pieces (8 cm diameter) of each
192 bioactive EVOH film with final doses of 333, 666, 1665 and 3330 μg of each EOC
193 per piece were attached on the base of the Petri dish lid with double sided
194 adhesive cellophane. The final doses of EOC per piece of film were calculated as

195 the product of content of each EOC in the film by grammage by film surface
196 (Section 2.1). Preliminary experiments were carried out to choose a suitable range
197 of concentrations for each EOC to be added to the EVOH films to obtain dose-
198 response curves.

199 All media in Petri dishes, with and without EVOH-EOC films, were centrally
200 inoculated with 15 μ L of a fresh conidia suspension (1×10^6 conidia/mL) of *F.*
201 *culmorum* or *F. proliferatum* and were immediately capped and sealed with
202 Parafilm M®. The three replicates of inoculated Petri plates of the same treatment
203 (a_w and type of film) were enclosed in sealed plastic containers together with
204 beakers of a glycerol–water solution matching the same a_w as the treatment to
205 maintain a constant equilibrium relative humidity inside the boxes. Treatments and
206 control cultures were incubated at 20 and 28 °C for 21 days in the darkness. All
207 experiments were run in triplicate and repeated twice.

208 2.5. Effect of treatments on fungal growth

209 Growth in treatments and control cultures was monitored every day during
210 the incubation period by measuring two diameters of the growing colonies at right
211 angles with the help of a magnifying glass and calculated. Colony radius was
212 calculated as the sum of the two diameters divided by four. The radial GR
213 (mm/day) was calculated as the slope of the line obtained by linear regression of
214 mean colony radius *versus* time (only the linear part of this plot was used). The
215 doses of EOC in the EVOH film/plate necessary for 50%, 90% and 100% growth
216 inhibition (ED_{50} , ED_{90} , and ED_{100}) (the last ED is also known as minimal inhibitory

217 concentration, MIC) were estimated when possible from the plots of GR vs EVOH-
218 EOC dose. All experiments were performed in triplicate and repeated twice.

219 2.6. Effect of treatments on mycotoxin production

220 2.6.1. Mycotoxin determination in milled maize cultures

221 At the end of the incubation period (21 days), regardless of the size reached
222 by the fungal colony, the total of culture (substrate plus fungal biomass) (approx.
223 25 g) in controls and treatments was removed from Petri dishes and dried at 45 °C
224 until constant weight was achieved. Then they were finely milled, homogenized
225 and analyzed for ZEA (*F. culmorum* cultures) and FB₁ and FB₂ (*F. proliferatum*
226 cultures) following the methodology described by Tarazona et al. (2020b). A
227 portion of milled culture (1–2 g) was placed into a Falcon tube and mycotoxins
228 were extracted shaking with 8 mL acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v) in
229 orbital shaker for 1 h. After centrifugation (4260 g, 5 min), two mL of the
230 supernatant was filtered through 0.22-µm PTFE syringe filter. Extracts from
231 cultures were diluted (1:2, v/v) with the same solvent before injection into the
232 chromatographic system. When mycotoxin levels were too high for the linear
233 calibration range, the extracts were appropriately diluted with the same solvent
234 mixture and injected again.

235 For calibration purposes, matrix-matched calibration was performed.
236 Mycotoxin standard solutions were obtained by dissolution of pure standards of
237 ZEA, FB₁ and FB₂ in acetonitrile:water (1:1, v/v) and further dilution with
238 acetonitrile/water/formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v). Calibration standards were prepared
239 by addition of variable volumes of ZEA, FB₁ or FB₂ standard solutions to extracts of

240 non-inoculated milled maize (blanks) prepared as indicated above for cultures.
241 Blanks were previously analyzed and found to contain no detectable amount of the
242 target mycotoxins. Aliquots of filtered blank extracts were diluted (1:2, v/v) with the
243 same extracting solvent. Then, aliquots of two mL of the diluted extract were
244 evaporated to dryness under a stream of N₂, added with appropriate volumes of
245 standard solutions and brought to a volume of two mL with acetonitrile/water/formic
246 acid (80:19:1, v/v/v) to provide the desired concentrations. The calibration range in
247 the diluted extract was 0.05–5.0 µg/mL for FB₁ and for FB₂ and 0.045–4.0 µg/mL
248 for ZEA. Calibration lines were obtained by weighted linear regression (weighting
249 factor 1/x) of the areas of peaks associated to the quantifier ion of each analyte vs
250 mycotoxin concentration.

251 The method was validated in-house by recovery assays and replication of
252 analyses as described by Tarazona et al. (2020a) with some modifications related
253 to mycotoxin concentrations and spiking levels in recovery assays. The
254 concentrations of mycotoxins in spiked blanks were in the ranges 2.5–200 µg/g for
255 ZEA, 5–150 µg/g for FB₁ and 3–50 µg/g for FB₂.

256 *2.6.2. UPLC-MS/MS conditions*

257 The separation and MS/MS conditions were as reported by Romera et al.
258 (2018). The UPLC–MS/MS system consisted of an ACQUITY UPLC™ system
259 (Waters, Manchester, UK), provided with an electrospray ionization interface (ESI)
260 that was used in positive ion mode (ESI+). Separation was performed at 25 °C in
261 an ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 column (50 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm particle size)
262 (Waters). The mobile phase was a time-programmed combination of water

263 containing ammonium formate (0.15 mmol/L) and formic acid (0.1%) (solvent A)
264 and methanol (solvent B) at a flow-rate of 0.37 mL/min. A volume of 30 μ L was
265 injected. MS/MS detection was performed by an ACQUITY TQD tandem
266 quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters Co., Milford, MA, USA). Two product ions
267 (1 quantifier, 1 qualifier) were monitored for each mycotoxin. Masslynx 4.1™
268 chromatographic software (Waters, Manchester, UK) was used for data acquisition
269 and processing. Retention time of the target peaks (quantifier and qualifier) in
270 multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) chromatograms was used for identification.

271 *2.7. Data analysis*

272 *2.7.1. Analysis of variance*

273 Data were analyzed by multifactor analysis of variance (ANOVA) using
274 Statgraphics Centurion XV.II statistical package (StatPoint, Inc., VA, USA). *Post-*
275 *hoc* Tukey's honestly significant difference (Tukey's HSD) ($\alpha = 0.05$) was usually
276 used to find homogenous groups when significant differences among the levels
277 were revealed by ANOVA. GR and concentrations values were transformed as log
278 ($x+1$) where x was the raw value of the variable to reduce spread.

279 *2.7.2. ML model development*

280 The compared ML methods for modeling fungal GR and mycotoxin
281 production in cultures were NN (neuralnet library) (Günther and Fritsch, 2010), RF
282 (randomForest library) (Liaw and Wiener, 2002) and XGBoost (XGBTree library)
283 (Chen and Guestrin, 2016). The used methodology has been described previously
284 (Tarazona et al., 2020a). For comparison purposes, a multiple linear regression

285 (MLR) model was also developed for every dependent output variable (outcome).
286 The equations have the general form in Eq. 1.

$$287 \quad Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (1)$$

288 where Y denotes the output variable, β_0 is an independent term (intercept), β_i are
289 the estimates of coefficients for X_i , which are the independent variables
290 (predictors), ε is the error term (unknown) and n is the number of predictors. The
291 software used was R and the ‘classification and regression training’ (caret)
292 package (Kuhn, 2016). The two species were treated separately. The input
293 variables were four (temperature, a_w , EOC type and EOC concentration). The
294 output variables were a) GR of *F. culmorum*, b) production of ZEA by *F. culmorum*,
295 c) GR of *F. proliferatum*, d) production of FB₁ by *F. proliferatum* and e) production
296 of FB₂ by *F. proliferatum*. The output values were the average of six
297 measurements to minimize uncertainty. Some preprocessing of variables was
298 performed. For mycotoxin outputs, the natural logarithm of average mycotoxin
299 concentration plus 1 was computed to avoid problems with undetectable
300 concentrations. Categorical variables were recoded into a set of separate binary
301 variables (indicator or dummy variables). Such recoding (dummy coding) was done
302 automatically by the statistical software R. For a variable with j levels, $j-1$ dummy
303 variables were created to avoid multicollinearity. The level that is not shown is the
304 reference level; the coefficients of the other levels are measured with respect to the
305 reference level. For the ML models, every data set (80 per output variable) was
306 randomly split into training (75%) and test (25%) sets. The training set was used to

307 build and validate the models and the test set was let aside to evaluate its
308 performance on independent external data, not previously shown to the models.
309 MLR is a linear regression method and does not require a time-consuming
310 procedure for parameter optimization; the coefficients are chosen to minimize the
311 sum of squares of the residuals (least squares method). The metric used for
312 performance evaluation of the ML methods was the averaged root mean square
313 error (RMSE) for training over 10-fold cross-validation. Cross-validation is a
314 resampling procedure used to evaluate ML models on a limited data sample. It
315 generally produces a less biased/optimistic estimate of the model skill than other
316 methods. In 10-fold cross-validation, the data is divided into 10 subsets. A holdout
317 method is repeated 10 times, such that each time, one of the 10 subsets is used as
318 the validation set and the other 9 subsets are put together to form a training set.
319 Thus, all observed values in the train subset are used for both training and
320 validation, and each observation is used for validation exactly once. The error
321 estimation (RMSE) is averaged over all 10 trials, which decreases bias because
322 most of the data are used for fitting, and reduces variance because most of the
323 data are used in validation set. The ML models were tuned to optimize their
324 performance for each one of the tasks, according to their most significant
325 parameters (Table 1). The R^2 (coefficient of determination) values were also
326 determined for each model and averaged over all ten-fold cross-validation. All
327 predictive models were tested and compared against a test dataset (25% of the
328 overall dataset) not used to train/cross-validate the models. The RMSE and R^2
329 values for these sets were obtained.

330 3. Results

331 3.1. Antifungal activity of bioactive EVOH-EOC films

332 Circular, easily visible and measurable colonies were observed on all fungal
333 cultures of the present study when growth occurred. Growth delay was 2–4 days
334 depending on culture conditions. The radial GR of *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum*
335 colonies vs doses in control and treatments under the different conditions assayed
336 are shown in Figs.1 and 2. No significant differences in radial GR were found in
337 control cultures without any film or with films without EOC, incubated under the
338 same conditions (temperature and a_w). Therefore, the values shown in Figs. 1 and
339 2 for control cultures of *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum*, respectively, are the
340 average of these six replicates (3 replicates each). The two species grew faster at
341 28 °C than at 20 °C and at 0.99 a_w than at 0.96 a_w . Under the same set of
342 conditions, the GR of *F. culmorum* was significantly higher than the GR of *F.*
343 *proliferatum*. Thus, their behavior was analyzed separately. In treatments, ANOVA
344 showed that the type of antifungal agent, EOC doses, and temperature significantly
345 influence the GR ($p < 0.05$) of *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum*. The GR of *F.*
346 *proliferatum* was also significantly influenced by a_w . The interactions antifungal
347 agent \times dose and temperature \times a_w (for *F. culmorum*) and the interactions
348 antifungal agent \times dose and antifungal agent \times temperature \times a_w (for *F.*
349 *proliferatum*) were significant ($p < 0.05$). Table 2 shows the homogeneous groups
350 obtained by the *post hoc* Tukey's HSD test. The presence of more than one group
351 is due to the existence of significant differences ($p < 0.05$). This test provided two
352 homogeneous groups for the type of bioactive EVOH films against *F. culmorum*

353 and the order of efficacy was EVOH-CIT > EVOH-IEG \approx EVOH-CINHO \approx EVOH-
354 LIN. For *F. proliferatum*, however, the Tukey's HSD test provided four
355 homogeneous groups for the bioactive films (one for each film) and the order of
356 efficacy was EVOH-CIT > EVOH-CINHO > EVOH-IEG > EVOH-LIN (Table 2).

357 Generally, for both fungi, the higher the dose the more efficient delay of
358 fungal growth. The four doses were arranged in three homogeneous groups (3330-
359 1665, 1665-666, and 333 μg /Petri plate) by the Tukey's HSD test (Table 2). In the
360 case of *F. culmorum*, the mycelium developed faster in controls than in treatments
361 with EVOH-CIT, regardless of doses. With EVOH-IEG, the two high doses (3330-
362 1665 μg /Petri plate) significantly decreased GR with respect to controls. With
363 EVOH-LIN, only the highest dose significantly decreased GR with respect to
364 controls (Tukey's HSD test). With EVOH-CINHO the Tukey's HSD test classified
365 doses and controls in a homogeneous group. In *F. proliferatum* cultures, GR was
366 significantly decreased by all the doses with respect to the controls, except for the
367 lowest dose (333 μg /Petri plate) with EVOH-LIN.

368 Table 3 lists the effective doses (EDs) of the different EVOH-EOC films/Petri
369 plate against *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* under all assayed conditions. The
370 EDs to reduce the GR of the fungi by 50, 90 and 100% (ED₅₀, ED₉₀ and ED₁₀₀)
371 were in the ranges 200 – >3330, 450 – >3330, and 660 – >3330 μg of EOC/fungal
372 culture, respectively, depending on the type of EVOH-EOC film, fungal species, a_w
373 and temperature. In general, with few exceptions, *F. culmorum* showed the
374 greatest susceptibility to all active EVOH films at 20 °C and 0.99 a_w . However, the
375 influence of environmental conditions on the susceptibility of *F. proliferatum* to
376 EVOH-EOC films was not clear and depended on the particular film tested. Thus,

377 for this species, the lowest EDs for EVOH-CIT films were recorded at 28 °C and
378 0.99 a_w , for EVOH-CINHO the combination 28 °C/0.96 a_w provided the lowest EDs.
379 Overall, considering the two species and all the temperature/ a_w combinations, the
380 lowest EDs were registered in the EVOH-CIT treatments and the highest EDs in
381 the EVOH-LIN treatments.

382 *3.2. Effect of bioactive EVOH-EOC films on mycotoxin production*

383 *3.2.1. Validation of the UPLC-MS/MS method*

384 For calibration lines, the R^2 values were > 0.99 and residuals were < 20%.
385 The average recoveries of ZEA, FB₁ and FB₂ in spiked blanks were 95.3%, 95.2%
386 and 96.0%, respectively. The average relative standard deviation (RSDr) of
387 recoveries (6 replicates per level) was < 5% for the three mycotoxins. Other
388 validation parameters agree with those previously reported (Tarazona et al.,
389 2020a).

390 *3.2.2. Production of mycotoxins*

391 In control cultures of *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* without any film or with
392 films without EOC, incubated under the same conditions (temperature and a_w) no
393 significant differences on ZEA, and FB₁ and FB₂ levels were found. Thus, the levels
394 of ZEA, shown in Fig. 3, and the levels of FB₁ and FB₂, shown in Fig. 4, for control
395 cultures of *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* are the average of the six replicates (3
396 replicates each).

397 ANOVA revealed that the main factors EVOH-EOC type, EOC dose and
398 temperature significantly influenced ZEA production by *F. culmorum* ($p < 0.05$) while

399 a_w did not. Two first order interactions (EVOH-EOC type \times dose and EVOH-EOC
400 type \times temperature) were significant. The *post-hoc* Tukey's HSD test ($\alpha = 0.05$)
401 (Table 4) discriminated two homogeneous groups: one composed of EVOH-CIT and
402 EVOH-IEG treatments and another group composed of EVOH-CINHO and EVOH-
403 LIN treatments. ZEA concentration decreased with increasing dose. The Tukey's
404 HSD test included each dose in a homogeneous group and there was not
405 overlapping (Table 4). Although ZEA levels were higher at 0.99 a_w than at 0.96 a_w ,
406 the differences were not significant ($p > 0.05$). Generally, ZEA production in controls
407 was significantly higher than in treatments. Interestingly, ZEA levels in treatments at
408 low LIN doses, 20 °C and 0.96 a_w exceeded the levels reached in controls (Fig. 3).
409 Correlation between $\log[C(ZEA)+1]$ and $\log(GR+1)$, where C(ZEA) is concentration
410 of ZEA, was significant ($R = 0.700$, $p < 0.0001$). The R^2 value (0.4905) indicates that
411 the model obtained by linear regression explains 49.05% of the variability in the
412 predicted variable.

413 According to multifactor ANOVA the main factors EVOH-EOC type, EOC
414 dose and a_w significantly influenced FB_1 production by *F. proliferatum*. The
415 interactions EVOH-EOC type \times dose, EVOH-EOC type \times temperature, and
416 temperature \times a_w were significant. The Tukey's HSD test placed the film types in two
417 homogeneous groups: one composed of EVOH-CIT and EVOH-CINHO and another
418 group composed of EVOH-IEG and EVOH-LIN (Table 4). The same test clustered
419 the EOC dose in two different groups: 1) 3330, 1665, and 666 μg /Petri plate and 2)
420 333 μg /Petri plate (Table 4). FB_1 level was significantly higher at 0.96 a_w than at 0.99
421 a_w . There were significant differences on FB_1 level between controls and treatments

422 under the same conditions. The factors EVOH-EOC type and EOC dose significantly
423 influenced FB₂ production but temperature and a_w did not. The homogeneous groups
424 depicted by Tukey's HSD test are shown in Table 4. Considering all treatments, there
425 was a significant positive correlation between $\log[C(\text{FB}_1)+1]$ and $\log(\text{GR}+1)$, where
426 C(FB₁) is concentration of FB₁, ($R = 0.828$, $p < 0.0001$). The R² value (0.686)
427 indicates that the linear model obtained by regression can explain 68.6% of the
428 variability in the predicted variable.

429 *3.3. ML methods applied to prediction of fungal growth and mycotoxin production*

430 Table 5 summarizes the characteristics of the best ML models found and
431 their RMSE and R² values. As previously explained, the goal was to obtain the
432 minimum average RMSE value for training with cross-validation but also
433 secondarily maximizing R².

434 For NN (single-hidden-layer perceptron) modeling, the optimal model
435 settings were selected using the lowest RMSE value for training with cross-
436 validation. Architectures with 5, 10 or 20 nodes in the hidden layer and a decay
437 value of 0.1, 0.2 or 0.3 were essayed (Table 5). The models giving the lowest
438 RMSE values usually provided the maximum R² values.

439 For RF, the ntree parameter was fixed to 500 for all the output variables and
440 the only parameter to modify was the number of randomly selected predictors to
441 sample every time a tree splits (mtry). There were four input predictors
442 (temperature, a_w, type of EVOH-EOC film, and EOC dose) so the tuning range of
443 values was mtry = [2, 3, 4]. The performance was best for mtry = 4, i.e. using all
444 input predictors (Table 5). The obtained average RMSE was lower than for the NN

445 or XGBoost. Thus, RF showed the overall best performance for predicting fungal
446 GR, and ZEA and FUM production. This was further confirmed with the test set.

447 XGBoost models have the largest number of parameters to tweak. Hence,
448 searching for optimal parameters takes more time than for NN and RF models.

449 Nevertheless, given the reduced size of data sets, the training time for all the
450 combinations listed in Table 1 is assumable. The best results were obtained from
451 models with the parameter values given in Table 5. Some parameter values given
452 in Table 1 were let constant (for example, nrounds = 150, as it was high enough to
453 achieve convergence in all simulations, gamma = 0, as increasing it makes the
454 algorithm more conservative, colsample_bytree = 1 (default), min_child_weight =
455 0.5). The optimal values for the variable parameters were max_depth (which
456 controls the maximum number of nodes allowed from the root to the farthest leaf of
457 a tree) = 2, 3 or 4 (depending on the output variable), eta (learning rate) = 0.1
458 (except 0.2 for *F. proliferatum* GR and 0.3 for FB₁ production), and subsample rate
459 (randomly sample a portion of the training data prior to growing trees at every
460 boosting iteration) = 1 (except 0.75 for *F. culmorum* GR) (Table 5). The best
461 XGBoost models produced minimal RMSE values for GR that were always higher
462 than the minimal RMSE values obtained with the best NN or RF models designed.

463 The R² values for the best XGBoost models were lower than the values obtained
464 for the best NN or RF models (except for ZEA production and *F. proliferatum* GR).

465 When comparing the relative accuracy of the models for predicting the GR of both
466 species it can be seen (Table 5) that the RMSE were lower and the R² were higher
467 for *F. proliferatum* than for *F. culmorum*. For MLR, an equation was obtained by
468 least squares regression using the 75% of the dataset for each of the five

469 outcomes. These equations included an independent term (intercept) and the
470 coefficient estimates for the predictor dummy variables.

471 Overall, the best performance for modeling fungal growth and mycotoxin
472 production was obtained using RF models, although differences with other tested
473 ML models were not high; for example, regarding ZEA production, the XGBoost
474 model provided a training RMSE of 1.041, very near to the value of 1.032 given by
475 the RF model (Table 5). They can be considered identical.

476 The results of the application of these models to the same dataset used for
477 testing (not used for training) appear in Table 6. The RMSE values were always
478 higher for the test set than for training, and the RF models achieved the best
479 (lowest) RMSE values. However, similar RMSE values were computed for the RF
480 and XGBoost models in the case of FB₂. For the test set, the MLR models
481 produced the highest RMSE values and the lowest R² values (Table 6). The
482 relative performance of NN and XGBoost changed depending on the selected
483 outcome. Fig. 5 shows the scatter plots of predicted *versus* observed values for the
484 RF and MLR models applied to the same test sets for GR of both *F. culmorum* and
485 *F. proliferatum*, and production of ZEA, FB₁ and FB₂. Negative predicted values
486 obtained with the MLR models have no sense; they were considered as zero. A
487 feature of RF is that there are not predictions (extrapolations) out of the bounds of
488 the observed output values. RMSE values can only be used to compare models on
489 a given outcome, not among them. For mycotoxins the computed outputs were
490 $\ln(C(\text{ZEA})+1)$, $\ln(C(\text{FB}_1)+1)$ or $\ln(C(\text{FB}_2)+1)$, where \ln denotes natural logarithm
491 and $C(\text{ZEA})$, $C(\text{FB}_1)$ and $C(\text{FB}_2)$ are concentrations of ZEA, FB₁ and FB₂,
492 respectively, as shown in Fig. 5.

493 **4. Discussion**

494 In the present study, the antifungal activity of EVOH-CINHO, EVOH-CIT,
495 EVOH-IEG and EVOH-LIN films in vapor phase against *F. culmorum* and *F.*
496 *proliferatum* under different regimes of a_w and temperature in partly milled maize
497 grains was tested. The effect of these treatments on ZEA production by *F.*
498 *culmorum* and FB₁ and FB₂ production by *F. proliferatum* was evaluated. Likewise,
499 the impact of possible interactions between environmental conditions and
500 treatments (type of bioactive film and doses) on fungal growth and mycotoxin
501 biosynthesis was also analyzed. In the present study, the inhibitory doses or
502 effective doses ED₅₀, ED₉₀, and ED₁₀₀ were studied. These parameters are usually
503 given to describe the response of filamentous fungi to antifungal agents and they
504 permit to perform comparative studies (Marín et al., 2013; Mateo et al., 2011b,
505 2013, 2017a; Sharma et al., 2017).

506 No previous studies on *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* growth and ZEA
507 and FUM production, respectively, in treatments with active EVOH films containing
508 EO or EOC have been reported so far. Lack of such reports hinders a critical and
509 comparative discussion of the results. However, previous results have shown that
510 growth of some *Fusarium* spp. may be inhibited by plant EOs (da Cruz Cabral et
511 al., 2013). In most of the reports, EOs are included within the culture medium.
512 Thus, Sharma et al. (2017) studied the effect of clove, lemon grass, mint and
513 eucalyptus EOs against *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* and they found MIC values
514 of 31.25, 62.5, 125 and 500 ppm, respectively, and fungicidal action at 125, 250
515 and 500 ppm, respectively. The lowest IC₅₀ (50% inhibitory concentration) values

516 were recorded for clove EO (18.22 ppm) followed by lemongrass (24.25 ppm), mint
517 (60.05 ppm) and eucalyptus (207.86 ppm), respectively. The inhibitory effect of
518 cinnamon, citral, *Litsea cubeba* oil, clove, eucalyptus, anise, spearmint and
519 camphor oils on *F. verticillioides* was investigated by Xing et al. (2014) and the
520 most effective of them was cinnamon oil. The MICs of cinnamon oil (85%
521 cinnamaldehyde), natural cinnamaldehyde (95%), and synthetic cinnamaldehyde
522 (99%) were 60, 50, and 45 mL/L, respectively. Hashem et al. (2010) using the agar
523 diffusion method found that EOs extracted from cumin, basil and geranium have a
524 significant antifungal activity against *F. oxysporum*, *F. solani*, *F. moniliforme* (*F.*
525 *verticillioides*), *F. dimerum*, *F. equiseti* and *F. lateritium*. The most effective EO was
526 cumin oil, the diameter of the fungal growth inhibition zone ranged from 2.17 to
527 0.00 cm depending on the fungal species and doses. The efficacy of clove oil
528 nanoemulsions on *Fusarium* growth and mycotoxin production during malting
529 process was explored by Wan et al. (2020). They observed that 1.5 mg clove oil/g
530 has a positive influence on barley grain germination and in the decrease in DON
531 levels and fungal biomass. They suggest the potential application of EO
532 nanoemulsion during the malting process. Dambolena et al. (2010) reported that
533 the oil of *Ocimum gratissimum* with high content in eugenol (95.5% – 70.1%) have
534 high effectivity (MIC 0.3 µL/mL) against *F. verticillioides* and it induces a significant
535 inhibitory effect on FB₁ production with respect to control ($p < 0.05$). Their results
536 showed a direct relationship between the inhibitory effects of EO on fungal growth
537 and FB₁ production. Seseni et al. (2015) found that lemongrass (84.8% citral),
538 clove (88.3% of eugenol) and thyme (63.1% thymol and 21.3% linalool) oils were
539 able to control the mycelial growth of *F. oxysporum* and *F. circinatum* at levels of

540 300–700 $\mu\text{L/L}$ of medium. Vilaplana et al. (2018) assayed *in vitro* thyme, mint,
541 rosemary and lavender oils against *F. verticillioides* on PDA. They found that
542 thyme oil was the best EO to control mycelial growth. The results of the *in vivo* test
543 showed the reduction of the severity of *F. verticillioides* on pineapples treated with
544 1000 $\mu\text{L/L}$, after 21 days at 8 °C plus 7 days of shelf-life at 20 °C. They suggested
545 that thyme oil might potentially be used to control fusariosis in pineapples during
546 postharvest, without negative effects on its physicochemical and sensory qualities.
547 The possible use of EOs in the control of *Fusarium* spp. is not limited to the fields
548 of agriculture and food; for example, Manganyi et al. (2015) found that clove and
549 thyme oils, as well as pure citral, eugenol and thymol at 500 $\mu\text{L/L}$, significantly
550 reduce radial growth colonies of *F. oxysporum* that form biofilm in contact lenses.
551 Total inhibition of all isolates was obtained when the EOs were used at a
552 concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{L/L}$. They demonstrated that clove and thyme oils
553 prevented mycelium cell attachment, biofilm development and caused total
554 inhibition of biofilm formation on soft contact lenses. They suggested that the use
555 of diluted clove and thyme oils could therefore be an option to prevent biofilm
556 formation of soft contact lenses. Even if all cited reports illustrate the effectiveness
557 of different EO against *Fusarium* spp., in none of them the EOCs included in our
558 films have been assayed. In addition, the diversity of used methodologies does not
559 permit a comparative critical study. However, in recent studies with relevant
560 aflatoxigenic and ochratoxigenic *Aspergillus* spp. using EVOH-EOC films and the
561 methodology applied in the present study, similar results were obtained (Mateo et
562 al., 2017a; Tarazona et al., 2018). Therefore, it can be concluded that EOC from
563 plants included in different packaging systems such as EVOH films, coatings,

564 paints, etc., which facilitate their controlled release, can be an excellent tool for the
565 prevention and control of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins in food, including cereals,
566 during silage, transportation or marketing.

567 The effect of films containing EOCs on ZEA production by *F. culmorum* and
568 FB₁ and FB₂ production by *F. proliferatum* has not been reported to date. Most of
569 the studies have focused on the production of aflatoxins or ochratoxin A (OTA) by
570 *Aspergillus* spp. (Mateo et al., 2017a; Nguyen Van Long et al., 2016; Tarazona et
571 al., 2018). However, some previous studies on the effect of different EOs
572 incorporated into culture media against closely related species, such as *F.*
573 *graminearum* or *F. verticillioides* have been published. Thus, Naven Kumar et al.
574 (2016) studied the inhibitory effect of *Curcuma longa* L. EO (53.10% ar-turmerone)
575 against *F. graminearum* and ZEA production in Sabouraud dextrose broth and in
576 maize grains. ZEA production was completely inhibited at 3000 µg/mL and 3000
577 µg/g, respectively. Marín et al. (2004) found that clove, lemongrass and palmarosa
578 oils at 500 mg/kg prevented ZEA production in maize grains only at 0.950 a_w/30 °C,
579 while cinnamon oil had no significant effect, and oregano oil stimulated ZEA
580 production. Considering that clove and cinnamon are high in eugenol and
581 cinnamaldehyde, respectively, these results do not completely agree with those
582 obtained in the present study, which may be because we have used pure
583 compounds (IEG, CINHO), different methodology and different *Fusarium* species.
584 Brado Avanço et al. (2017) found that the *Curcuma longa* L. EO decreased the
585 production of FB₁ and FB₂ by *F. verticillioides* in liquid medium. All the
586 concentrations of *C. longa* oil tested (17.9–294.9 µg/mL) caused a statistically
587 significant decrease in fumonisin production. The 294.9 µg/mL concentration

588 caused the strongest inhibition (about 90%). A direct correlation between the
589 inhibitory effect of fungal growth and the synthesis of FB₁ and FB₂ was observed.
590 Dambolena et al. (2010) found that *O. basilicum* EO from Sagana and Kariti
591 (different locations in Kenya) do not inhibited FB₁ production by *F. verticillioides*.
592 The first EO contained mainly LIN (more than 95%), while the second EO
593 contained geranial (49.6%) and neral (30.9%) as the main constituents. However,
594 *O. gratissimum* EOs were found to induce a significant inhibitory effect on FB₁
595 production with respect to control ($p < 0.05$). They suggest that the high activity of
596 the oil from *O. gratissimum* can be attributed to their high eugenol content (95.5–
597 70.1 %), which agrees with our results. EVOH-IEG was better inhibitor of FB₁ and
598 FB₂ production by *F. proliferatum* than EVOH-LIN, although the differences were
599 not significant (Table 4).

600 In the food industry, EOs could also be directly mixed into the initial food
601 formulations. This method may result in excessive amount of EO and produce
602 changes in the taste and flavor of the food. Direct surface application of EOs, such
603 as fumigation, may result in a rapid evaporation of active agents. Thus, in the last
604 years many antimicrobials are incorporated at packaging material, particularly films
605 (Nguyen Van Long et al., 2016; Zhu, et al., 2016). Usually, EOs have proved to be
606 more efficient in the vapor phase than with direct application (Aguilar-González et
607 al., 2015; Reyes-Jurado et al., 2019). Application of films containing EOs allows the
608 active principle to migrate to the coating surface and provides a continuous
609 antimicrobial effect on the food during extended exposure. Use of polymers as
610 carriers of antimicrobials not only permits controlled release of these antimicrobials
611 but also prevents dramatic reductions in their antimicrobial activities due to their

612 affinity for food particles and inactivation by components in foods. It also reduces the
613 amount of active agent required, satisfying consumer demand for fewer additives.
614 Antimicrobial film materials must contact the surface of the food if active principle is
615 non-volatile. EOs and their components are gaining popularity due to their volatile
616 nature, which facilitates the use of small concentrations that are safe for
617 consumption (Sivakumara and Bautista-Baños, 2014) and sensory properties of
618 food are less affected. Paris et al. (2020) provide recent outcomes on the
619 antimicrobial effectiveness of EOs in the vapor phase. We have also assayed EVOH
620 films containing EOCs as a possible strategy to control the growth of toxigenic
621 *Aspergillus* spp and in the partial or total inhibition of aflatoxins and OTA biosynthesis
622 (Mateo et al., 2017a; Tarazona et al., 2018). However, its effectiveness to control
623 the growth of *Fusarium* spp., including *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum*, and
624 production of their associated mycotoxins is reported for the first time in the present
625 study.

626 Regarding the predictive models developed in the present study, the best
627 overall performance in terms of average RMSE and R^2 for the training datasets and
628 for test on unseen datasets was given by RF models while the MLR models provided
629 the worst performance. These parameters were generally better for training than for
630 testing, as expected (Tables 5 and 6). Regarding the test set, XGBoost models
631 provided similar performance to RF for predicting FB₂ and outperformed NN for
632 predicting ZEA production while NN models ranked second for the prediction of FB₁
633 concentration.

634 There are very few reports concerning ML applications in the field of predictive
635 mycology. Therefore, a comparative critical analysis of their application to predict

636 fungal growth and mycotoxin production is difficult. Within NN methodology, Multi-
637 layer perceptron (MLP) and radial-basis function networks (RBFN) were applied to
638 build up a model of the joint effect of a_w , pH and temperature to predict the maximum
639 specific GR of the fungus *Monascus ruber*. NN architectures provided better
640 predictions for the maximum specific GR of the fungus than classical polynomial
641 models in relation to three input variables. This agrees with our study although the
642 input variables are not the same and the fungal species is different. The ranges of
643 the R^2 values for the RBFN, the MLP NN, and the polynomial model indicated better
644 fit of the experimental data to the RBFN-based approach (Panagou et al., 2007;
645 Panagou and Kodogiannis, 2009). A RBFN was developed and compared against a
646 quadratic response surface model for predicting the specific GR of the
647 basidiomycetous fungi *Physisporinus vitreus* and *Neolentinus lepideus*; even when
648 both models gave reasonably good predictions, the performance of the RBFN was
649 superior to that of the classical statistical method (Schubert et al., 2010). Mateo et
650 al. (2009) compared RBFN and MLP with 1-2 hidden layers to predict OTA
651 accumulation in grape juice cultures of *Aspergillus carbonarius* over a range of a_w ,
652 temperature and doses of the fungicide carbendazim. They found that training was
653 faster for RBFN than for two-hidden-layer perceptrons, but the overall performance
654 was worse. These ML approaches were also used to predict deoxynivalenol
655 production in cultures of *F. culmorum* in barley seeds under different conditions of
656 temperature, a_w , inoculum size, and incubation time. Single-hidden-layer
657 perceptrons with a low number of hidden nodes proved better than two-hidden-layer
658 perceptrons, but the performance depended on the training algorithm. The RBFN

659 reached lower errors and better generalization than MLP but they required a high
660 number of hidden nodes (Mateo et al., 2011a). Tarazona et al. (2020b) performed a
661 comparative study of NN, RF and XGBoost models to predict the growth of *F.*
662 *culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* and production of ZEA and FUM in treatments with
663 different formulations of three chemical fungicides. In that case, XGBoost models
664 provided slightly better results. Fast NNs were used to model the antimicrobial
665 activity of 49 EOs and the output data reflected the activity of these EOs against four
666 common pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans*,
667 and *Clostridium perfringens*) as measured by standardized disk diffusion assays;
668 NNs were able to predict >70% of the antimicrobial activities (Daynac et al., 2015).
669 NNs with genetic algorithm models and surface response models were found
670 operative and reliable in optimizing the minimum effective dosage of tested EOs for
671 *Candida* spp. Such models reduce the number of experiments and shorten the time
672 needed for determining the optimal antifungal doses of EOs (Perić, et al., 2019). RF
673 and gradient boosting machine (GBM) predictive models were applied to describe
674 and predict prevalence of *Listeria* spp. in feces and soil samples based on
675 meteorological factors at the farming location. Both models performed very well,
676 similarly for the feces models, but the soil GBM model outperformed the soil RF
677 model. According to the authors, they can be used in pastured poultry farms
678 environments (Golden et al., 2019).

679 **5. Conclusions**

680 Our results show *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* grew more rapidly at 28 °C
681 than at 20 °C and at 0.99 a_w than at 0.96 a_w . Under the same set of conditions, the

682 GR of *F. culmorum* was significantly higher than the GR of *F. proliferatum*. Fungal
683 growth and ZEA and FUM production depended on a_w , temperature, and treatment
684 (type of EVOH-EOC film and EOC dose). Considering the efficacy of the EVOH-
685 EOC films assayed, as reflected by the ED values, inhibition of fungal GR, blockage
686 of mycotoxin biosynthesis, cost and availability of the EOC, EVOH-CIT followed by
687 EVOH-IEG and EVOH-CINHO are proposed as the most promising candidate for
688 treatments against *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* and as inhibitors of ZEA and
689 FUM production. At present, implementation of lethal EOC doses against toxigenic
690 *Fusarium* spp. in food, as a single effective measure to prevent fungal development
691 and mycotoxin production, may become unreliable. However, knowledge of ED₅₀,
692 ED₉₀ and ED₁₀₀ of EOCs under standardized conditions can be very useful in food
693 technology (longer expiration periods, reduction of other chemical preservatives or
694 application of complementary treatments, etc.). The few studies carried out to date
695 in which ML methods have been applied to predict growth of toxigenic fungi and
696 mycotoxin production suggest that these methods can be extremely useful in the
697 prevention and proper management of these risks. In the present study, among the
698 ML models studied, RF models were able to predict GR of *F. culmorum* and *F.*
699 *proliferatum*, and mycotoxin (ZEA and FUM) production better than NN, XGBoost
700 and MLR models.

701 **Declaration of competing interest**

702 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests
703 or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported
704 in this paper.

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945 Figure captions

946 Fig. 1. Radial growth rates (GR) of *F. culmorum* in cultures on partially milled maize
947 grain incubated with EVOH films containing cinnamaldehyde, citral, isoeugenol or
948 linalool at different doses in vapor phase under different a_w and temperature
949 regimes. Incubation period: 21 days. Error bars represent standard deviations.

950 Fig. 2. Radial growth rates (GR) of *F. proliferatum* in cultures on partially milled
951 maize grain incubated with EVOH films containing cinnamaldehyde, citral,
952 isoeugenol or linalool at different doses in vapor phase under different a_w and
953 temperature regimes. Incubation period: 21 days. Error bars represent standard
954 deviations.

955 Fig. 3. Zearalenone production by *F. culmorum* in cultures on partially milled maize
956 grain incubated with EVOH films containing cinnamaldehyde, citral, isoeugenol or
957 linalool at different doses in vapor phase under different a_w and temperature
958 regimes. Incubation period: 21 days. Error bars represent standard deviations.

959 Fig. 4. Fumonisin B₁ and B₂ production by *F. proliferatum* in cultures on partially
960 milled maize grain incubated with EVOH films containing cinnamaldehyde, citral,
961 isoeugenol or linalool at different doses in vapor phase under different a_w and
962 temperature regimes. Incubation period: 21 days. Error bars represent standard
963 deviations.

964 Fig. 5. Scatter plots and line of best fit of predicted output values provided by the
965 predictive models *versus* observed (experimental) output values for test datasets.
966 The outcomes were GR and ZEA production for *F. culmorum* and GR and FB₁/FB₂

967 production for *F. proliferatum*. RF: random forest model; MLR: multiple linear
968 regression model. For mycotoxins, the natural logarithms of concentration plus 1
969 were computed as output values

Table 1

Main parameters for each machine learning (ML) model and their tuning values.

ML Model	Parameter name	Description	Values
Neural network	<i>size</i>	Hidden layer units (nodes)	[5, 10, 15, 20]
	<i>decay</i>	Weight decay rate	[0.1, 0.2, 0.3]
Random forest	<i>mtry</i>	Number of randomly selected predictors	[2, 3, 4]
	<i>ntree</i>	Number of trees	500
Extreme gradient boosted tree	<i>nrounds</i>	Number of iterations	150
	<i>max_depth</i>	Maximum tree depth	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5]
	<i>eta</i>	Learning rate or shrinkage	[0.1, 0.2, 0.3]
	<i>gamma</i>	Regularization penalty factor	0
	<i>colsample_bytree</i>	Fraction of columns to be randomly sampled for each tree	1
	<i>min_child_weight</i>	Minimum instance weight per node	0.5
	<i>subsample</i>	Subsample ratio from training set to grow the trees	[0.5, 0.75, 1]

Table 2

Arrangement of homogeneous groups by *post hoc* Tukey's HSD test ($\alpha = 0.05$) within EVOH-EOC film type, EOC dose, temperature and water activity with regard to their effects on *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* growth rate on partly milled maize kernels.

Factor	Level	Fungal species	
		<i>F. culmorum</i>	<i>F. proliferatum</i>
		Growth rate	Growth rate
		Low → high	Low → high
EVOH-EOC film type	CIT	●	●
	CINHO	●	●
	IEG	●	●
	LIN	●	●
Dose (μg EOC/Petri dish)	333	●	●
	666	●	●
	1665	● ●	● ●
	3330	●	●
Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	20	●	●
	28	●	●
Water activity (a_w)	0.96	●	●
	0.99	●	●

Within each column, the levels containing a black circle form a group of means within which the Tukey's HSD test does not find statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$). Black circles in the same row denote overlapping.

Table 3

Effective doses (ED₅₀, ED₉₀ and ED₁₀₀) in vapor phase of EVOH films containing cinnamaldehyde (CINHO), citral (CIT), isoeugenol (IEG) or linalool (LIN) (μg /fungal culture in 9-cm Petri dish) against *F. culmorum* and *F. proliferatum* on partly milled maize under different environmental conditions.

Fungi	T (°C)	a _w	EVOH-CINHO			EVOH-CIT			EVOH-IEG			EVOH-LIN		
			ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₁₀₀
<i>F. culmorum</i>	20	0.96	2500	>3330	>3330	455	625	660	1100	>3330	>3330	2150	>3330	>3330
		0.99	510	1330	1660	200	450	660	240	1400	3330	470	>3330	>3330
	28	0.96	570	2400	3330	225	540	660	290	>3330	>3330	640	>3330	>3330
		0.99	3080	>3330	>3330	300	590	660	1650	>3330	>3330	645	>3330	>3330
<i>F. proliferatum</i>	20	0.96	490	630	660	435	620	660	1920	3330	>3330	1600	>3330	>3330
		0.99	495	630	660	490	630	660	1670	>3330	>3330	>3330	>3330	>3330
	28	0.96	480	630	660	460	625	660	1740	>3330	>3330	>3330	>3330	>3330
		0.99	615	>3330	>3330	430	617	660	670	>3330	>3330	>3330	>3330	>3330

Table 4

Arrangement of homogeneous groups by *post hoc* Tukey's HSD test ($\alpha = 0.05$) within EVOH-EOC film type, EOC dose, temperature and water activity with regard to their effects on production of zearalenone (ZEA) by *F. culmorum* and production of fumonisins (FB₁ and FB₂) by *F. proliferatum* on partly milled maize kernels. Incubation time: 21 days.

Factor	Level	Fungal species		
		<i>F. culmorum</i>	<i>F. proliferatum</i>	
		ZEA	FB ₁	FB ₂
		Low → high	Low → high	Low → high
EVOH-EOC film type	CIT	●	●	●
	CINHO	●	●	●
	IEG	●	●	●
	LIN	●	●	●
Dose (µg EOC/Petri dish)	333		●	●
	666		●	●
	1665	●	●	●
	3330	●	●	●
Temperature (°C)	20	●	●	●
	28	●	●	●
Water activity (a _w)	0.96	●	●	●
	0.99	●	●	●

Within each column, the levels containing a black circle form a group of means within which the Tukey's HSD test does not find statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 5

Best machine learning (ML) model performance for predicting growth rate (GR) and ZEA production by *F. culmorum* and GR, and FB₁/FB₂ production by *F. proliferatum* cultured on partly milled maize with EVOH films containing cinnamaldehyde, citral, isoeugenol or linalool.

Output variable	ML model tested	Best model parameters	RMSE ^a	R ²
<i>F. culmorum</i> GR	NN ^b	size = 5, decay = 0.3	1.936	0.868
	RF ^c	ntree = 500, mtry = 4	1.803	0.886
	XGBboost ^d	<i>max_depth</i> = 3, <i>eta</i> = 0.1, <i>subsample</i> = 0.75	2.243	0.814
ZEA production by <i>F. culmorum</i>	NN	size = 5, decay = 0.3	1.130	0.684
	RF	ntree = 500, mtry = 4	1.032	0.708
	XGBboost	<i>max_depth</i> = 3, <i>eta</i> = 0.1, <i>subsample</i> = 1	1.041	0.736
<i>F. proliferatum</i> GR	NN	size = 10, decay = 0.1	0.608	0.940
	RF	ntree = 500, mtry = 4	0.563	0.948
	XGBtree	<i>max_depth</i> = 2, <i>eta</i> = 0.2, <i>subsample</i> = 1	0.687	0.965
FB ₁ production by <i>F. proliferatum</i>	NN	size = 5, decay = 0.1	0.599	0.886
	RF	ntree = 500, mtry = 4	0.593	0.914
	XGBboost	<i>max_depth</i> = 3, <i>eta</i> = 0.3, <i>subsample</i> = 1	0.859	0.824
FB ₂ production by <i>F. proliferatum</i>	NN	size = 20, decay = 0.1	0.449	0.900
	RF	ntree = 500, mtry = 4	0.428	0.916
	XGBboost	<i>max_depth</i> = 4, <i>eta</i> = 0.1, <i>subsample</i> = 1	0.444	0.894

^a Root mean squared error

^b NN: Neural network (single-hidden-layer perceptrons)

^c RF: Random Forest

^d XGBtree: Extreme gradient boosted trees (the following parameters had constant values: nrounds = 150, gamma = 0, colsample_bytree = 1, min_child_weight = 0.5)

Table 6

Performance of the ML models (Table 5) for predicting GR and ZEA production by *F. culmorum* and GR, and FB₁/FB₂ production by *F. proliferatum* cultured on partly milled maize with EVOH films containing EOC on a test set not used for model design.

Output variable	Model tested	RMSE ^a	R ²
<i>F. culmorum</i> GR	NN ^b	2.395	0.771
	RF ^c	2.248	0.840
	XGBoost ^d	2.708	0.726
	MLR ^e	2.914	0.654
ZEA production by <i>F. culmorum</i>	NN	1.283	0.480
	RF	1.031	0.654
	XGBoost	1.254	0.525
	MLR	1.324	0.480
<i>F. proliferatum</i> GR	NN	0.721	0.916
	RF	0.618	0.957
	XGBoost	0.712	0.928
	MLR	0.929	0.879
FB ₁ production by <i>F. proliferatum</i>	NN	0.822	0.772
	RF	0.861	0.822
	XGBoost	0.992	0.745
	MLR	1.484	0.493
FB ₂ production by <i>F. proliferatum</i>	NN	0.605	0.772
	RF	0.501	0.847
	XGBoost	0.503	0.857
	MLR	1.426	0.617

^a Root mean squared error for test

^b NN: Neural network (single-hidden-layer perceptron)

^c RF: Random Forest

^d XGBoost: Extreme Gradient Boosted trees

^e Multiple linear regression

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

a) *Fusarium culmorum*